

MICROSTRUCTURE AND FRACTURE IN SiC WHISKER

REINFORCED 2124 ALUMINUM COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The microstructures of extruded and hot-rolled 2124 Al-15% (by weight) SiC whisker composites have been examined. The whiskers in the extrudate were preferentially aligned along the extrusion direction. This preferred orientation resulted in anisotropic mechanical properties; there was approximately a 20% difference in the strength between the longitudinal and transverse directions. Hot rolling (85% reduction in thickness) along the original extrusion direction caused some damage of the whiskers but they still retained their original orientation. In contrast, hot rolling perpendicular to the extrusion direction tended to rotate the whiskers and, consequently, produced a nearly isotropic material. Whisker-free zones, which were frequently found in the as-extruded material, were virtually eliminated or greatly reduced in size by hot rolling. The rolled material showed a significant improvement in tensile elongation which may be attributed to the more uniform microstructure that resulted from the hot rolling.

In situ Auger fractography of the composite was also carried out. The results indicated that the interfacial bonding between the SiC and Al matrix was good and that Al₂O₃ played an insignificant role during the course of fracture of the composite. A vacuum degassing study was also conducted on both the elemental powders from which the composites were manufactured and the consolidated material. It is demonstrated that degassing appears to have no effect on the subsequent mechanical properties of the composite.

Introduction

It has been demonstrated that SiC whisker reinforced aluminum (SiC_w/Al) exhibits many interesting properties which are attractive for structural application. However, the materials also have some limitations, particularly low tensile ductilities and low fracture toughnesses. These limitations inhibit the use of SiC_w/Al in a wide range of structural applications. In order to improve these properties, it is necessary to understand the metallurgical factors that govern fracture. There are many

factors involved in fracture, including: (1) the strength of the whisker-matrix interface, (2) the presence of oxides, (3) defective whiskers, (4), the presence of intermetallics, including impurities in SiC_w powder, and (5) microstructural inhomogeneities, e.g., precipitate free zones, whisker free zones and heterogeneous dislocation distribution. As many of these factors are interrelated, it is difficult, if not impossible, to separate each individual item and to evaluate it.

The first part of this paper describes modifications to the microstructure of SiC/Al composites by hot rolling and evaluates the effect of these microstructural changes on subsequent mechanical properties and in particular on the tensile ductility. The second part of the paper is an in situ Auger fractographic study of the composite which provides information on the nature of the interfacial bonding between SiC_w and Al and the role of residual oxides during fracturing of the composite. The presence of oxide in the composite is due to powder metallurgy (PM) processings of the material. Also, because of the PM processings, residual gas contents, particularly hydrogen, are expected to be high. Therefore, the last part of this paper deals with the degassing behavior of both the powders and consolidated SiC_w/Al composites. The effect of vacuum degassing on the mechanical properties are also discussed.

Experimental Results and Discussion

a. Microstructure

Figure 1 is an optical micrograph of extruded 2124Al-15% SiC_w in the T4 condition. Several important features are noted in the microstructure. First, over half of the reinforcements actually have a particulate shape as opposed to the whisker shape which was the case for the majority of the original SiC powders. Nevertheless, those SiC whiskers that have aspect ratios (length/diameter) of greater than unity, are preferentially aligned along the extrusion (longitudinal) direction. The high mechanical strength in the longitudinal direction by comparison with the transverse direction is primarily due to this preferred orientation of the whiskers. However, some of anisotropy may also be due to the crystallographic texturing of the aluminum matrix as the result of extrusion. For example, although it has been reported⁽¹⁾ that SiC particulate reinforced 6061 Al exhibited only a small amount (5%) of mechanical anisotropy attributable to the extrusion texture in the Al matrix, for whisker reinforced composite the anisotropy is expected to be higher. In this study it is measured to be about 15 to 20% for 2124 Al-15% SiC_w . The second feature of the microstructure is the high impurity content appearing in the matrix. The impurities are either from the original SiC powders or are products of the alloy matrix during consolidation. The former impurities are characterized as irregular particulates which normally show sharp edges and are of dimensions less than $5\mu\text{m}$, while the latter impurities are intermetallic inclusions which have a smoother morphology and occasionally show dimensions of roughly $10\mu\text{m}$. Also, in the optical micrograph, the intermetallics appear to be grey in contrast to the nearly black particles from the original SiC powders. The intermetallics are identified as Fe, Cr, Mn-rich particles produced during the composite fabrication. These intermetallics are potentially detrimental to the toughness and tensile ductility of the composite.

Figure 2 is a typical fracture surface of the composite. It is noted that in addition to the large local plasticity in the matrix, which often has been observed⁽²⁾, there is also a large number of brittle regions which are undoubtedly intermetallic inclusions. We will present the experimental evidence for this conclusion later in the paper.

Figure 1 Microstructure of 2124 Al-15% SiC_w extrusion.

20 μm

Figure 2 Typical fracture surface of 2124 Al-15% SiC_w extrusion. Brittle intermetallics frequently appear on the fracture surface.

The third feature is the presence of bands of SiC whisker-free zones (of 5 to 10 μm width) in the microstructure. The effect of this inhomogeneous microstructure is not yet clear. However, it may lead to inhomogeneous plastic flow when the material is under stress and, consequently, could result in premature tensile failure.

The fourth feature is the presence of defective whiskers. Defects in the whiskers are either present in the original whisker or are produced during the consolidation of the composite. Figure 3 is an example showing the breakage of the whisker during material processing. In fact, many of the SiC whiskers have entirely lost their whisker identities and virtually converted into particulates. The damage in the whiskers not only reduces the load transfer capability of the whiskers but also provides sites for crack initiation and propagation. Therefore, it is expected that both the mechanical strength and elongation to failure are affected by the whisker damage. The intrinsic defects in the whiskers cannot be observed in the photomicrographs but have been reported and discussed by many researchers^(3,4) using Transmission Electron Microscopy. In summary, the whisker, by its nature of growth, is highly defective. It has many microvoids inside the core region, microtwins and stacking faults along the length of whiskers and often exhibits a serrated surface. All these characteristics can significantly degrade the mechanical properties of the composite by nucleating cracks either at the SiC surface or in the core. Since SiC is notch-sensitive, the stress that is required to break the whisker is much less than that predicted from the case of an ideal whisker. In addition, the microtwins and stacking faults in the whisker may further accelerate the fracturing processes and, consequently, result in low ductility and toughness of the composite. However, direct evidences of whisker breakage during plastic deformation is difficult, if not impossible, to obtain. The relative importance of the intermetallics and defective whiskers to the fracture behavior of the composite is an interesting technical issue. The fracture of SiC_w/Al composite is, in general, catastrophic, i.e., crack propagation or growth is in a relatively fast fashion. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the fracture of the composite is dominated by crack initiation. Although the tensile ductilities of the composite are almost the same for both the longitudinal and transverse orientations, the tensile strengths in the two perpendicular orientations are different by roughly 20 percent (or about 140 MPa). Since the load transfer to the whiskers in the case of testing along the longitudinal direction is higher than it is along the transverse direction, the results suggest that the whisker can tolerate more stress than the intermetallic prior to fracturing. The exact conclusion, of course, depends on the size, distribution and nature of the intermetallics produced during the composite fabrication and will be discussed later.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 are microstructures of the sheet materials produced by hot rolling with rolling direction parallel (longitudinal) and perpendicular (transverse) to the original extrusion direction, respectively. Many features are readily noticeable. Whisker orientation is more random in the rolling plane for the sample that was rolled transversely than the one that was rolled longitudinally. This results in a decrease of strength in the longitudinal direction but an increase of strength in the transverse direction. The composite becomes, surprisingly, a virtually isotropic material, as evidenced by the fact that the same mechanical strength is measured in the two perpendicular directions. In contrast, rolling along the original extrusion direction tends to maintain the whisker orientation and results in mechanical anisotropy similar to that in the original extrusion. Also, the mechanical strength of the rolled sheet is almost identical to that of extrusion in the same orientation and under the same heat treat conditions, indicating that hot rolling produces insignificant

Figure 3 Whisker breakage during fabrication of the composite.

Figure 4 Microstructure of the rolled sheet. Rolling direction is the same as the original extrusion direction.

Figure 5 Microstructure of the rolled sheet. Rolling direction is perpendicular to the original extrusion direction.

whisker damage. Another major observation is the diminishing whisker-free-zones in the rolled sheets. Apparently, the whisker-free-zones, which are essentially aluminum-rich regions, were preferentially deformed during the rolling operation. This leads to the elimination of the whisker-free-zones and, subsequently, a more uniform microstructure in the rolled materials. A uniform microstructure is certainly beneficial to the mechanical properties, especially the ductility and toughness, of the material. In fact, the ductility of the rolled sheet was found to be much greater than that of the extrusion, sometimes a hundred percent improvement over the extrusion. However, it would be naive to entirely attribute the improvement to the uniform microstructure since the geometry of the test samples are different. In the case of extrusion, the test samples were cylindrical bars in which plane-strain condition prevails, while plane-stress condition is valid for the rolled sheet. Further study is necessary to evaluate the net effect of test sample geometry and uniform microstructure.

Fractographic analysis of SiC/Al composites is difficult due to the large amount of reinforcements in the matrix and, also, many of the potential sites that may originate the crack. This is particularly true for extrusion materials. It is not only because of the difficulties in location of the fracture origin in the material, but also the complex nature of the fracture origin, e.g., intermetallics, whiskers and whisker-matrix interfaces, etc. Fortunately, it seems to be less of a problem for rolled material. In rolled material, the fracture origin can normally be identified with bulky and brittle intermetallic inclusions. Figure 6 shows the typical fracture surface, fracture origin and EDAX from a SiC/Al sample. The fracture undoubtedly initiated from the intermetallic inclusion, which is Cr, Mn, Fe and Cu rich in composition and has a dimension, surprisingly, of over 50 μm . Intermetallic inclusions of that size have not been observed in the extrusion sample. Apparently, it is due to the long-time high-temperature exposure of the material during the rolling operation. This observation demonstrates the importance of intermetallic inclusions to the fracture behavior of the SiC/Al composite and, in fact, it is the dominant factor controlling the fracture in the rolled material.

b. In Situ Auger Fractography

As mentioned earlier, many factors are involved in the fracture of the composite and they are all, somewhat, interrelated. Direct observation of the fracture of SiC_w/Al by conducting in situ tensile test using High Voltage Transmission Electron Microscopy (HVTEM) is impractical. This is because the diameter of the whisker is relatively large with respect to the finite penetration depth offered by HVTEM. The effective volume for the electron beam is relatively small, which means an extensive TEM study is necessary to provide enough statistical information on the fracture mechanisms. In addition, because of the thinness of the TEM foil the stress-strain state in the material, especially at the whisker-matrix interface, may be significantly modified by the free surfaces. This certainly limits the usefulness of the results obtained from such a study.

There are some simple experiments that can be performed to provide useful information about the fracture mechanisms in SiC_w/Al. An example is in situ Auger fractographic study of the composite. In these experiments, pre-notched impact samples were first cooled in liquid nitrogen and then fracture in situ in an Auger Electron Spectroscopy which was normally maintained at an extremely high vacuum (10^{-7} - 10^{-8} Pa). Analyses of fracture surfaces were conducted afterwards.

50 μm

Figure 6 Fracture origin in rolled material. EDAX shows the intermetallics are rich in Cr, Fe, Mn and Cu.

Figure 7 is a typical AES spectrum of the fracture surface of a $\text{SiC}_w/2124$ Al impact sample immediately after fracture. The spectrum shows the presence of Al, Mg, Cu, C, O and a small amount of Si on the fracture surface. The amounts of Mg and Cu measured from the fracture surface are consistent with the values for their bulk concentrations in the 2124 Al alloy. Carbon and oxygen are two common absorbants found in many Auger analyses, even at extremely high vacuum. It is necessary to be careful, therefore, in interpreting their presence. Since the amount of SiC in the composite is relatively large (15% by weight), it is believed that the C signal is due to the whisker phase. However, the interpretation of the presence of oxygen is more subtle.

One of the major findings from the general Auger spectra of many test samples is that the spectral intensity for Si, which comes mainly from SiC, is much too low to account for the proper bulk concentration of SiC. The spectral intensity for Si is greater for the sample fractured transversely compared to the one fractured longitudinally because of the preferred orientation of the SiC whiskers. However, it is still lower than that expected. This observation result indicates that there was little whisker pull-out. Also, sputter etching of the fracture surface causes the spectral intensity of Si increase, indicating that the SiC that is present must be coated with Al from the matrix. Both results suggest that the bonding between SiC whiskers and 2124 Al matrix is quite good. This has also been proposed by Marcus⁽⁵⁾ based on his study of $\text{SiC}_w/6061$ Al. This conclusion is further supported by scanning electron microscopic examination of the fracture surface. Figure 8 is a fracture surface of 2124 Al-15% SiC_w . It is apparent that the amount of SiC whiskers exposed is lower than that expected from the bulk content of SiC in the composite. In addition, higher magnification shows that most of the exposed whiskers are clearly coated with the Al matrix. Similar observations have been reported in $\text{SiC}_w/6061$ Al⁽⁵⁾.

As mentioned earlier, Al is a strong oxide former and it tends to adsorb oxygen from even an extremely high vacuum (10^{-7} Pa) environment. Consequently, oxygen analysis from the fracture surface must be conducted relatively quickly before the surface is contaminated. Also, it is necessary to determine whether the oxygen was adsorbed from the environment or was actually in the material originally. The chemical state of the oxygen in the former is elemental and in the latter is an oxide. Since the Auger spectra for pure Al and Al_2O_3 are different, one can distinguish the chemical state of the oxygen on the fracture surface by measuring the shape of Al spectra, particularly in the high energy regime. Figure 9 shows a typical Al spectrum from the fracture surface. In order to make a direct comparison, the standard spectra⁽⁶⁾ for Al and Al_2O_3 are also shown in the figure. The test results clearly show that the oxygen is in an elemental state and is not in an oxide form. The measured high-energy Al spectrum (from 1300 to 1400 eV) may not coincide exactly with that shown in the standard, which is often due to the off calibration of the instrument at the high-energy end. However, the most important feature is that the shape of the two spectra are almost identical. It should be noted that the tests do not exclude the existence of small amounts of Al_2O_3 . They simply show that Al_2O_3 does not play an important role in the fracture of the composite. In particular, the Al_2O_3 -Al interface does not act as preferential path for crack propagation in the composite. Otherwise, one should have observed highly distorted Al spectrum, namely, spectrum from pure Al but strongly weighted by that from Al_2O_3 , since the penetration depth of the Auger electrons is normally about two to three atomic layers.

Figure 7 Auger spectrum from the fracture surface of 2124 Al-15% SiC_w composite.

5 μm

Figure 8 A typical fracture surface of 2124 Al-15% SiC_w. The apparent amount of SiC whiskers exposed is lower than that expected from the bulk content of SiC in the composite.

Figure 9 Al spectrum from the fracture surface of 2124 Al-15% SiC_w failed in high vacuum (10⁻⁷ Pa). In order to make a direct comparison, the standard spectra for Al and Al₂O₃ are also shown.

Several attempts have been made to study the oxygen distribution on the fracture surface and to identify the chemical state of the oxygen at some discrete high-oxygen regions. However, serious problems were often encountered. First, oxygen mapping is highly impractical because of continuous oxygen adsorption from the environment. Second, because of the fine surface irregularity, which resulted from the local plastic deformation during fracture, it is difficult, if not impossible, to conduct a meaningful analysis at a localized region. Also, it is worth noting that elemental analysis of the depth profile by sputter etching is less meaningful because of the inherent shadowing effect that is due to the contoured surface.

It is interesting to note that in this study impurity particles have often been observed on the fracture surface of the composites. They have been identified to be Ca-rich and, sometimes, contain Na also. Neither Ca nor Na is expected to be present in the 2124 Al-SiC_w composite. They were apparently introduced during the material fabrication. The effect of these contaminants on the fracture of the composites is not clear at present. However, the frequent exposure of these particles on the fracture surface suggests that the bonding between them and the Al matrix is probably not strong.

In summary, it is demonstrated, by using in situ Auger fractography, that the oxide plays an insignificant role in fracture of the composite. In addition, the interfacial bonding between the SiC whiskers and the Al matrix is shown to be good. These observations suggest that the fracture of these composites is probably limited by other factors such as excessive intermetallic inclusions, or faulted SiC whiskers⁽³⁾.

c. Vacuum Degassing

Another experiment was carried out to study the effect of residual gas, particularly hydrogen, on the mechanical properties of SiC_w/Al. It has been well demonstrated^(7,8) that vacuum degassing of the residual gases from PM SiC/Al prior to welding is necessary in order to produce a good weldment of the material. The degassed species includes nitrogen, oxygen, hydrogen and other organic compounds. It is generally believed that hydrogen is the major element responsible for poor weldments through the generation of microporosities during fusion welding. While the effect of hydrogen on the embrittlement behavior in Al alloys is still controversial⁽⁹⁾, there is plenty of evidence^(10,11) suggesting that the presence of hydrogen in Al may be detrimental to its ductility. This forms the basis of studying the effect of vacuum degassing on the ductility of SiC_w/Al. The technique used to identify degassing species which evolved during heating is Temperature Programmed Thermal desorption Mass Spectrometric (TPTD/MS) analysis.

The standard procedure involves placing metal powder (0.05 g to 0.5 g weight) in a quartz and allowing ultra-pure helium to sweep over the sample inside the tube in a continuous fashion (20 to 40 ml/min at 7×10^4 Pa gas pressure) so that any degassed species are swept into the mass spectrometer via a heated (100°C) thin walled stainless steel transfer line and a glass jet separator. The jet separator is a necessary portion of the apparatus, and is used to fractionate the mixture of degassed species present in the helium such that species of low molecular weight (helium, hydrogen) are reduced to around 1/30th of their original concentration while species of higher molecular weight are reduced, but only by 1/2 to 1/3 typically. This allows approximately 1 ml/min of total gas flow into the high vacuum system of the mass spectrometer while maintaining a relatively rapid flow rate through the quartz tube sample holder. This rapid flow rate provides almost

instantaneous response to various gasses, e/g., H₂, N₂ and H₂O, which are injected into the flowing helium system. Finally, the mass spectrometer continuously monitors the species which degas from the sample as the tube is heated from ambient to a high temperature (850°C herein) at a fixed rate (16.10°C/min herein). A brief description of the experimental apparatus has been reported elsewhere⁽¹²⁾.

Figure 10 is a summary of the ion chromatograms for the 2124 Al/SiC_w powders mixture after heating from a temperature of 250°C to 850°C. The degassed species include H₂, H₂O, CO₂ and a series of organic decompositions. H₂O emissions occur at several stages and this is consistent with results from some of the other Al powders⁽¹³⁾. The 105°C peak may represent the emission of the physisorbed water, while the 270°C and 330°C peak emissions represent some specific oxide dehydration reactions. For example, the reaction $Al_2O_3 \cdot 3H_2O = Al_2O_3 \cdot H_2O + 2H_2O$ is known to occur readily at temperatures above 200°C. Also, the m/e = 44 spectrum is marked as CO₂, one of the common absorbants found in atmospheric environment. The spectrum may also be attributed to some organics, e.g., C₃H₈. Similarly, the m/e = 28 spectrum can be identified as N₂, CO or C₂H₆. The various organic hydrocarbons appearing in the samples are believed to be due to the handling of the powders, as they are usually sorted in plastic bags prior to further processing. The data obtained from TPTD/MS analysis is very useful in terms of material fabrication, as it clearly demonstrates that a 450°C vacuum heat treatment is a feasible way to degas the powder mixture.

TPTD/MS analysis was also conducted with consolidated SiC_w/2124 Al. However, no gaseous species was evolved until the temperature almost reached the melting point of the Al alloy matrix. This was expected since the degassing mechanism for the powder is different from that for the consolidated material. For the former it is a surface desorption phenomenon, which is primarily temperature dependent, but for the latter, it is a diffusional phenomenon, which is both temperature and time dependent. TPTD/MS analysis is not sufficient to provide data with the outgas schedule for the consolidated material. Additional information about the hydrogen diffusivity in Al, D_H is necessary. In spite of the large discrepancy on the activation energy for D_H (14-16), the actual values of D_H at 450-500°C range seem to be in good agreement from all research groups. If one assumes the equation $X = (2D_H t)^{1/2}$, where X is the diffusion distance and t is the time, then an estimation of 20h at 500°C in vacuum would be sufficient to remove the excessive hydrogen from a 12.7 mm thick specimen. In fact, it has been shown⁽⁸⁾ that vacuum (5 x 10⁻⁴ Pa) degassing of SiC_w/Al at 500°C for 24 h can reduce the hydrogen level by nearly half, namely, from 6-7 ppm for the as-received material to 3-4 ppm (by weight) for the degassed condition. 2124 Al-15% SiC_w composite extrudate was, therefore, degassed at 500°C for 72 h in vacuum (10⁻⁴ Pa) and subsequently heat treated and tested. The test results are presented in Table 1. In order to make a direct comparison, identical samples which were not degassed were also tested and these data are also presented in the Table

Apparently the data for the degassed samples are essentially the same within the data scatterband as that for the samples that were not degassed. These results suggest that either the vacuum degassing is insignificant to the mechanical properties of the as-received SiC_w/2124 Al extrudate, or the degassing schedule used is not thermally sufficient to remove the excessive residual hydrogen. However, vacuum degassing at higher temperature and longer time would be impractical from the application point of view.

Figure 10 TPTD/MS analysis of 2124 Al-15% SiC whisker powders mixture. It shows 450°C in vacuum is sufficient to degas the powders.

TABLE 1. EFFECT OF VACUUM DEGASSING
ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES
OF 2124 Al/15% SiC_w

Conditions	E, GPa	σ_y , MPa	σ_t , MPa	ϵ_f , %
Not degassed, T4	102.1	397.7	596.6	3.5 + 0.3
T6	103.8	435.8	565.0	2.5 ± 0.4
Degassed, T4	103.8	369.0	620.1	3.4 + 0.4
T6	103.4	450.7	638.6	3.0 ± 0.4

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